

Polarographic Behaviour of Carbohydrates: Part 1. Glucose and Maltose in Phosphate Buffer

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Polarographic behaviour of glucose and maltose has been studied in phosphate buffer at pH 8.0. Each of them has been found to give a small reduction wave controlled by the rate of a preceding ring $\rightarrow$ aldehyde transformation. The 'ring form' has been postulated to be the nonreducible species and the aldehyde form to be the reducible species. A mechanism of reduction is proposed.

ALTHOUGH aldehydes are known to be reduced at the dropping mercury electrode Heyrovsk'y and Smöler¹ failed to detect any reduction wave for monosaccharides such as glucose, arabinose, mannose, etc. and for disaccharides such as maltose, lactose and sucrose. Cantor and Peniston² however obtained small reduction waves for the above monosaccharides at relatively high concentration. Wiesner³ showed that the limiting currents of these compounds are controlled by the rate of transformation of nonreducible ring form of aldose to the reducible open chain form. Subsequently different aspects of the polarographic behaviour of monosaccharides have been investigated rather thoroughly by several workers.⁴⁻⁸ But the polarographic behaviour of disaccharides such as maltose and cellobiose has not been studied properly although Kerr⁹ obtained a small reduction wave for maltose in KCl solution. It was therefore thought desirable to carry out a thorough comparative study of the polarographic behaviour of glucose and maltose in buffer solution.

Experimental

Materials: Pure α -D glucose and maltose were supplied by B.D.H. and by May and Baker (London) respectively. The compounds were stored over Magnesium perchlorate in a vacuum desiccator and used without further purification. All reagents and chemicals were of A.R. grade.

Apparatus: A Cambridge pen recording Polarograph was used for recording the current-voltage curves. A saturated calomel electrode was used as the reference electrode. The DME had the following characteristics: drop time = 2.2 sec; rate of flow of

mercury = 4.3mg/sec in distilled water at a mercury reservoir height of 60 cm.

Buffer solutions were prepared by mixing carbonate-free 0.2M KOH with 0.2M potassium dihydrogen phosphate solution. pH measurements were carried out with a Cambridge bench type pH meter

Method: Solution of glucose/maltose in phosphate buffer (pH 8.0) was prepared and thermostated at 25° for half an hour for completion of mutarotation and for attaining the temperature of the bath. It was then deoxygenated by bubbling electrolytic hydrogen gas through the solution for 5 min prior to each measurement.

Results and Discussion

General polarographic behaviour: A small but well-defined reduction wave of maltose was obtained with a 1.0M maltose solution in phosphate buffer (pH 8.0). The height of this wave was observed to decrease with time and ultimately to reach a constant value after about half an hour. This is due to the mutarotation process in which the β -form of maltose is converted into the α -form in solution. The limiting current of this equilibrated maltose solution has been found to decrease linearly with decreasing maltose concentration down to ca 0.25M, below which it disappeared. It has also been found to be independent of the height of the mercury reservoir, which shows that the electrochemical reduction is controlled by the rate of a preceding chemical reaction. The limiting current as well as the half-wave potential of maltose has been found to be dependent upon the pH of the medium. With increasing pH of the medium half wave potential was shifted towards more negative potential region while the limiting current has been found to increase with increasing pH of the medium. It is clear from this observation that rate of the preceding chemical reaction is enhanced by increasing hydroxyl ion concentration resulting in increasing limiting current. The high temperature coefficient of the limiting current (found

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to be about 5 per cent per degree) also confirms the kinetic nature of the limiting current

Glucose has been found to give a small reduction wave at relatively high concentration (Ca. 0.1M) in phosphate buffer (pH 8.0). The limiting current of the wave has been found to be concentration dependent but is independent of the height of the mercury reservoir. It has also been found to increase with increasing pH or increasing temperature of the medium. The temperature coefficient of the limiting current for *d*-glucose has been to be about 17 per cent per degree.

Mechanism of reduction of maltose: It is clear from the above discussion that polarographic behaviour of maltose is very much similar to that for *d*-glucose. Like *d*-glucose highly concentrated solution of maltose gives rather small polarographic wave, the limiting current of which is kinetic in nature. Since the maltose molecule contains a reducible glucose unit it is expected to be reduced in a similar way. We therefore, postulate, by analogy, that the 'ring form' of maltose (I) is not reducible at the DME but the aldehyde form (II) is reducible. The rate of reduction is controlled by the rate of ring $\rightarrow$ aldehyde transformation, which is enhanced by hydroxyl ions. The overall reduction process may be represented as follows:

Formation of the free aldehyde form during the mutarotation process is also supported by the formation of oximes, semicarbazones and osazones of

maltose¹⁰⁻¹² which are typical aldehydic reactions. The most conclusive evidence in favour of the above mechanism is that glucose-1-¹⁸O undergoes oxygen exchange with water more than thirty times slower than the mutarotation process^{13,14} thus excluding the only other reasonable pathway, i.e., one involving exchange of the hydroxyl group at C(1) with water¹⁵. This also excludes the formation of an aldehydrol form as a necessary intermediate in the mutarotation process

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References

1. J. HEYROVSKÝ and I. SMOLER, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1932, **4**, 521.
2. S. M. CANTOR and D. P. PENISTON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 2113.
3. K. WEISNER, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1947, **12**, 64.
4. P. DELAHAY and J. E. STRASSNER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 893.
5. J. M. LOS and K. WIESNER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 6346.
6. J. M. LOS, L. B. SIMPSON and K. WIESNER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 1564.
7. W. G. OVEREND, A. R. PEACOCKE and J. B. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3487.
8. T. IKEDA and M. SENDA, *Bull. Chem. Soc., (Japan)*, 1973, **46**, 2107.
9. R. W. KEER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 2735.
10. J. W. HAAS, J. D. STOREY and C. C. LYNCH, *Anal. Chem.*, 1962, **34**, 145.
11. J. W. HAAS and R. E. KADUNCE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 4910.
12. R. T. MORRISON and R. N. BOYD, "Organic Chemistry", Allyn and Bacon, Inc., Boston, 1974, p. 1112.
13. T. TITANI and M. GOTO, *Proc. Imp. Acad (Tokyo)*, 1940, **16**, 398.
14. D. RITTENBERG and C. GRAFF, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3370.
15. B. Capon, *Chem. Rev.*, 1969, **69**, 454.